

SOME SYNTACTIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH ORAL SPEECH AND THEIR ANALYSIS FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF CONCEPTS OF CORRECTNESS OF SPEECH.

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ABSTRACT

Finding orthological mistakes and its effect on language learning process is essential step for extracting knowledge about it. Anytime we face a lot of changes and losing grammatical structures in English speaking. Of course those situations lead to difficulties in grasping the language by its learners, as well as many contradictions, as well as to emergence of controversial situations. There are also cases of misunderstanding of the oral speech. when we logically think of or look through its environment we can execute some good performance in creating effective teaching learning situation in our classroom. Orthological analyses of English spoken language can play a central role in making it good, accurately expressed, clear, exemplary speech. This article discusses the same things, explains points with examples, emphasizes some sides and certain aspects of English oral speech, and shows how important the correctness of English oral speech in reaching the intended purposes.

First of all, it is more accurate and appropriate to clarify the concept of speech before speaking about it more. What is the speech, itself? What is its role like in interaction and why is it necessary for peoples' association properly?

Speech is an outside appearance of a text that is organized and arranged by a speaker, an orator or a writer to reach what is implied in any situation, and it is not only a language-related phenomenon, but also a spiritual and aesthetic phenomenon. Therefore, when evaluating it as an exemplary speech, it is assumed that the intended purpose of the listener and the reader is to reach the intended purpose, to have a certain effect on them, and to make certain requirements before the speech. These requirements dictate that grammatical speech is correct, that words are accurately expressed, that words should be beautiful, vivid and expressive. Speech Teaching - Orthology deals with the study of these qualities. Orthology is the study of linguistic norms.¹ the word comes from Greek *ortho-* ("correct") and *-logy* ("science of").

Correctness of Speech.

Correctness of speech is its main communicative feature. Properly organized speech can provide quick and easy understanding of both sides - the speaker and the listener, the writer and the reader. If the speech is not correct, it is neither logical nor expedient. V. G. Kostomarov stated once, "Correctness is a necessary and prerequisite for the culture and nature of speech, that it is a strict and accurate correspondence with the accepted norms of literary language at a time, its pronunciation, orthographic, vocabulary and understanding accuracy." **2.** That is why we can say, the correctness of the speech is first its correspondence with most a literary language criteria.

The importance of the meaning stress in oral speech.

Proper speech requires two basic principles: stress (accent) and grammar. Some syllables on some words, that is, the emphasis on the word, are not the same in all languages. For example, in Russian and in English, stresses may be on different parts of the words, but in Uzbek it is generally on the last words. In this context, if we concentrate on the English stress better, the words' stress will change as the they get suffixes. For example:

word to hear	shape	total syllables	stressed syllable
PHO TO GRAPH		3	#1
PHO TO GRAPH ER		4	#2
PHO TO GRAPH IC		4	#3

3.

It is best to keep that principle in the pronunciation. However, we must not overlook the fact that, in some cases, the meaning may change as the vocabulary moves. This is the case in English. Take the word *project*, for example. When you look at this word without a word stress, it is difficult to know what it means. The stress is on the realization of its meaning, that is, when the *pro * ject* stressed on the first syllable, the action is understood as *to cast an image*; if the stress is placed on the last syllable, like *proje*ct*, it means *an undertaking*. In English these words are quite common: pre * sent - prese * nt, e * xport - expo * rt, i * mport - impo * rt, co * ntrast - contra * st, o * bject - obje * ct. Without distinguishing these features from the words, the wrong use of the accent is caused and the meaning of the word is distorted. These situations should be considered by others aside from language learners, especially by educational and cultural workers (teachers and instructors etc). Many English speakers have been dissatisfied with the use of the accent by many English language learners, non-native speakers and native speakers. We can see this in the following words: *For a few words, native English speakers don't always "agree" where to put stress. For example, some people say teleVIsion and others say TELevision. Another example is: CONTroversy and conTROversy.***4.**

We have now seen how the meaning of the word can be differentiated by the word-stress on the words. The meaning-stresses on words can also cause changes in the content and subtitles of the sentence. For example, John ate the apple emphasizes each of the words, taking into account who ate the apple, what he ate or what he did:

a. *John* ate the apple.

[focus on *John*, rather than *Bill, Joe*, etc]

b. John *ate* the apple.

[focus on *ate*, rather than *saved, threw*, etc]

c. John ate *the apple*.

[focus on *the apple*, rather than *grapes, pears*, etc]

Now let's analyze:

||It was `JOHN |who ate the `APple||

||What John did with the `APple |was `EAT it||

||What ate |John| the APple|| 5.

In such cases, logical stress is needed to emphasize the meaning of each word. However, there are instances where failure to properly use the vocabulary, as in the syllabus, can lead to distortions. For example, pay attention to the use of the phrase "*A child cannot be happy without mother*"

Or we can say "a motherless child cannot be happy"-What does that mean? Does it mean a child who has lost mother(a child is an orphan) or does it mean a child who is not with his mother right now (his mother might be somewhere, far from her child right now). In this sentence meaning is more confused.

Do you think about a child who has no mother? - it will remain dark and unknown to the listener or the reader. Only the stress on the word can clarify it. The first meaning, in the word child, is understood as the second. So, in order to make sense of the meaning of the speech, we must pay attention to the correct use of the verbal and the stress of word in the sentence.

Incorrect usage of pronouns.

For a person we always tend to use with a "who", but we find that many English speakers use "that" instead. Today, even in the media, it is a testament to our thinking: "Those students that find this unpleasant ..." "The people in the factory that worked hard were rewarded." We also find it difficult to misuse the 'who' diamond elsewhere, for example: "Companies who have empowered their workers ..." "A manufacturer who produces quality products ..." "Companies who emphasize quality ..." 6.

Singular or plural usage problems in speech.

The pronouns "They", "their" and "them" are not common pronouns, that is, it is not appropriate to use them for horses that come in unity, but for some reason it has now been neglected, and such cases are still in use today: "If you want to hire an employee, you must pay them. " "If a company wants to make money, they must please their customers." "Recognition makes an individual feel important and is something they can brag about." "An employee is paid a certain amount for their work."6.

There is also a violation of syntactic norms in speech. When we syntactically analyze certain speech patterns in some of the works, we can see such disturbances. An example of a word violation is It looks like it will rain. Of course, if we pay attention to this, we will fully understand the error: the grammatical word should be used before the horse, otherwise it will

be a mistake and will cause difficulty in understanding. The rule should be that the girl looks like her mother and that is the right thing to do.

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If we stick to the content of our previous sentence, we should look like this: It looks as if it will rain. There are many such cases in the world: I drug myself out of bed this morning. // A tall, thin man with owlsh spectacles and a bald head. // Bailey, the new striker, looking as if he would burst with pride. // 'Well-bred individuals sometimes break some of the rules; but to break them and get away with it, you first have to know them. "7.

The tone also plays a role in the proper and appropriate expression of meaning. Depending on how words are accentuated, meanings may change. For example, in the speech, "What brought you here?" The words such as sincerity, whispering, mocking, protesting can only be realized with the help of tone.

Speech is one of the main communicative qualities of speech. . The language and the thinking are at the forefront. This is because the harmony between things and events in nature and society, and their reflection in speech, is just that.

Thus, accuracy is the consistency and coincidence of the word itself.

Accuracy can also be interpreted differently. This is the word and its common sense, as well as its use in speech.

Obviously, clarity as a key feature of speech is, first of all, related to the lexical level in the language system. The term "Speech Accuracy" refers to the vocabulary that is the word and the vocabulary that is expressed in the language.

So which of the following languages is the most appropriate for the production of exemplary speech? Although they are closely related to each other, they differ in terms of meaning. Differences in these areas allow you to select and use them. Take, for example, synonyms of vestige, sign, mark, indication, hint, remnant, proof. Although they form a synonym for a common sense, it is not always possible to use one instead of the other. Examples of Ulr include clothing, brands of goods, signs of times, indication of illness, general hints of writing, remnants of materials, and so on. It is not possible to call good fortune just to be good, or to be well-planned, or to be well-planned. Because the word wowl is mainly used for good horses, and the word "wowl" is used for action. However, we often see that the English language is ignored by this rule. This can be seen in the following examples:

She is not well. (well = adjective)

She is well qualified. (well = adverb) 8.

Speech also includes small words that are not present in the written speech. As you analyze your speech, you may even be surprised to see how well, just and oh, the words are used repeatedly:

You can see the obvious in the dialogue below (youth chat game Scruples):

C: Do you put them face down - hang on

H: Oh - ha

C: Then we get one ballot card each and you put them aside until the vote is called

V: Oh – sorry

C: Did we decide you were the dealer - yes - we did

V: Oh - that was right

C: Oh it's just that the player to the left of the dealer starts play by becoming the first - asking the player to pose a dilemma

H: Oh - what do I do - oh I take one of these

V: Oh

C: Oh - hang on hang on **9**.

Oh and well the words have been assigned to several names. They can be called discurs signs or verbal labels.

They are not in any grammatical form and are not compatible.

"Good" in the interview process is neither good nor bad. They often occur:

Well what do you think? Well I'm not really sure. **10**.

It can be difficult to translate these spoken words into our native language, and it is difficult to determine the meaning or place in the sentence. However, they are often overused in oral speech. Some reports suggest that speaking English speakers as a second foreign language increases their speech activity when they use these spoken words.

For this reason, setting boundaries for word recognition is more complex and requires learning the language and how to use it within functional styles. It is helpful to summarize the above comments and conclude the following.

Speech is a manifestation of language, a form of realization, an event that has a material (natural, physical) form, which is given directly to observation. There are two different forms of speech, their emergence The use varies depending on the composition. On the one hand, these processes are inextricably linked to each other and can influence each other. Verbal speech, in other words, is a process that is free and naturally occurring, in contrast to written speech, while written speech is based on speech, but it is structured, It is an element that is molded into several forms and serves as a standard for all. The speech is, as we have said earlier, the linguistic identity of the people within the daily formal, informal, and free communication of the people.

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